

ISSN:2814-063X

BASUG LAW JOURNAL

BASUG

LAW JOURNAL

Volume 2 | Issue 3
September, 2024

**A Publication of:
Faculty of Law,
Sa'adu Zungur University**

VOL. 2, ISSUE 3, 2024

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2024**

BASUG Law Journal Volume 2 Issue 3 2024

Published by:

Faculty of Law,

Sa'adu Zungur University (formerly Bauchi State University)

For more information, see: www.basuglawjournal.com

To order:

Faculty of Law,

Bauchi State University, Gadau

No: 65, Kano-Kari Road,

Misau,

Bauchi State.

ISSN: 2814-063X

THIS JOURNAL SHOULD BE CITED AS BASUGLJ Volume 2 No 3 2024

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EDITORIAL NOTE

It is with immense pleasure and pride that we present to you the third issue of the Bauchi State University (BASUG) Law Journal, marking our second publication for the year. This issue stands as a testament to the tireless commitment of our contributors, whose scholarly work continues to push the boundaries of legal scholarship in Nigeria and beyond.

We are particularly elated by the diversity and depth of the submissions received for this edition, not only from across Nigeria but also from international scholars. The topics covered reflect the evolving and multifaceted nature of legal discourse in contemporary society.

These papers, among others, cover a vast range of legal fields, reflecting the dynamic interplay between law and society. We believe the breadth of scholarship featured in this issue will contribute meaningfully to academic discourse and legal practice.

We would like to extend our profound appreciation to the Faculty of Law, Sa'adu Zungur University, for their unwavering support as our publisher. Our sincere gratitude also goes to the Management of Sa'adu Zungur University for their continued encouragement and partnership in ensuring the success of this journal.

We are deeply indebted to the contributing authors for their invaluable research and dedication to advancing legal knowledge. Their work remains at the heart of what makes this journal a beacon of academic excellence.

Finally, we thank you, our esteemed readers, for your continued engagement with the BASUG Law Journal. It is through your readership that this publication finds purpose, and we hope that this issue serves as both a valuable resource and a source of inspiration for future legal thought and action.

Sincerely,

Prof. S. M. G Kanam
Chairman of Editorial Board and Dean
Faculty of Law,
Sa'adu Zungur University

CONTENTS

Editorial Board_____	iv
Editorial Note_____	v
Articles	
An Assessment of the Medico-Legal and Ethical Issues in Surrogate Motherhood	
Agbo Friday Ojonugwa, Mary Arthur Jolasinmi, Grace Perpetual Dafiell_____	1
Examination of Islamic Takaful Insurance Model in Nigeria Vis-À-Vis the Powers of the National Insurance Commission (NAICOM)	
Ochenehi Dominic Sunday, Mohammed Bashir Saidu_____	19
Appraising The Jurisdiction of the Court and Competition and Consumer Protection Tribunal in Prosecuting Electricity Consumer Complaints in Nigeria	
Alfred M. Tijah, Kwaghkehe Ierkwagh_____	31
The Powers of the Central Bank of Nigeria On Currency Redesign: The Extend of Compliance with Law in 2023 Naira Redesign Policy	
Ibrahim Danjuma_____	53
An Analytical Review of the Constitutional Right to Life and Health	
Samuel UGBO, Omagbemi-Ariko Mercy Ebere_____	88
Health Response for Gender-Based Violence Survivors	
Adekilekun Medinat Adeola_____	109
Legal and Institutional Framework for The Establishment of the World Trade Organization (WTO): Trends, Challenges and Prospects for Nigeria	
Umar Abubakar Dubagari, Muhammad Waje Bawa_____	127
Environmental Non-Governmental Organisations and Their Status in Protecting the Environment	
Stella.O. Idehen_____	148
An Assessment of the inadequacies of personnel towards curbing Commercial Malpractices in Markets in Nigeria: Hisbah Institution as an option	
Ismail Danjuma Yusuf, Fatimah Tanimu Bindawa_____	164

Exploring Protections Available to Minority Members Under Nigerian Corporate Law

Shamsuddeen Magaji, Abubakar Garba Salisu _____ 183

One Man One Court: The Perils of Solitary Decision over Appeals at High Court

Lilian Ifeoma Nwabueze _____ 201

Recognising Corporate *Zakat* Under Nigerian Corporate Law as a Means of Alleviating Poverty in North-Eastern Nigeria

Shamsuddeen Magaji _____ 216

The Responsibilities and Sanctions of International Law During Armed Conflict: A Case Study of Russia and Ukraine War

Ibrahim Danjuma _____ 230

International Law and Diplomacy: Challenging The “Fixity” of State Sovereignty

Nelson E. Chegwe, Michael C. Ogwezzy _____ 254

Jurisdictional Issues and Choice of Law in E-Commerce in Nigeria

Amaayeneabasi Ini Enang _____ 271

Without Justice, Law Labours in Vain: A Critique of the Judgment of the Supreme Court of Nigeria in APC V. Bashr Sheriff & 3 Ors. (Lawan V. Machina)” SC/CV/1689/2022

Taiwo Olawoye Lawrence _____ 287

Comparative Study on the Enforceability of Contract of Restraint in Trade

Habila Isah Barau, Ibome Habila Bulmen _____ 318

Legal Implications and Limitations of the Executive Immunity clause in Nigeria

Ayub O. Mohammed _____ 336

The Utility of Wasiyya under Nigerian Contemporary Society

Alhaji Ahmed Rufai _____ 348

A Conceptual Discourse on Protecting the Rights of Electronic Commerce Consumers in Nigeria

Muhammad Nuruddeen _____ 356

ONE MAN ONE COURT: THE PERILS OF SOLITARY DECISION OVER APPEALS AT HIGH COURT

By

Lilian Ifeoma Nwabueze*

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.13853390

ABSTRACT

Appeals appear to be last hope of litigants in any adjudication process. It is often insignificant whether the appellant is right or wrong. What seems to be the determining factor is that a perceived miscarriage of justice has been identified by any of the parties in a case and same should be examined by a court higher than that from which the appeal is emanating from. The constitution guarantees all, the right of appeal but the exercise is a matter for the party who so desires to carry out. A party may wish to appeal against a judgment but may be constrained after undertaking the first appeal due to lack of resources even though his case may be genuine. Therefore, at any level where an appeal can be heard, extra effort should be taken to ensure that what the law requires has been followed and that may include incorporating the knowledge and experiences of more than one judge so that justice would not only be done but will be seen as been done. The paper finds that solitary jurisdiction of State High Courts while sitting over appeal matters limits both judicial and judicious appraisal of cases filed for judicial review. A less negative implication of which is the continuous search for justice at other appellate levels while at the other extreme, the cause of justice may be truncated. The paper recommends a review of the composition of State High Courts in its appellate jurisdiction so that more than one judge should determine appeal cases to give proper effect to the provisions of the constitution on the same and as it stands with other courts of coordinate jurisdiction. Also, practice directives can be used by State Chief Judges to streamline the number, qualification and experience of judges to preside over appellate cases. The paper has confirmed that robust decisions would emerge from appellate adjudications presided over by more than one judge at the High Court.

Keywords: High Court, Solitary Decisions, Appellate Jurisdiction, Appellate Decisions, Truncated Justice

1. INTRODUCTION

State High Courts and other Courts of co-ordinate jurisdiction are included in the Courts properly described as courts of superior record.¹ The courts are so described because their establishment, composition and jurisdiction are determined by the provisions of the constitution.² Thus, while sitting as a trial court or in its appellate or supervisory capacity, proper recording of its proceedings and findings are observed as same can either determine the case or be the ground for further appeal at a higher court.³

The High Court can most likely be labelled as an intermediate court in the hierarchy of all courts of competent jurisdiction within a nation and as the superior judiciary in the State or Province where it is located. The former description is earned because it occupies a position higher than the grass root courts such as the Magistrate Courts and the District/Area Customary Courts but lower than the other appellate courts namely; the Court of Appeal and the Supreme Court. As identified in the latter description, the High Court is the highest judicial organ of a State though it may have coordinate status with other Courts within the State. Thus, the Court has the onerous task of ensuring that the judicial affairs of a State are stabilized and that justice is maintained through constitutional provisions.

The judicial functions of a State High Court tend to justify not only the middle position it occupies in the hierarchical representation of courts in Nigeria but also as the recognized judiciary of a State.⁴ The judgment of a State High Court over a matter in dispute may be given judicial approval and not that made by a Magistrate Court except where the decision of the latter is upheld when reviewed by the former where the need arises.⁵ In the same way, the decision of the Court of Appeal over a matter on appeal from a State High Court supersedes that made by the latter court where the two decisions are at variance in all material facts.⁶ Therefore, any cause of action

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¹ Section 6(5) of the 1999 Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria (hereinafter referred to as the Constitution)

² Sections 255-257 of the Constitution

³ The Nigerian Law School 'Council of Legal Education Course Handbook on Civil Procedure' (Bar Part II Course; 2007/2008 edn., Abuja) p 7

⁴ *ibid*

⁵ *ibid*

⁶ *ibid*

adjudicated upon may be finally determined through the decision of a State High Court or the same decision may be the necessary foundation upon which further judicial exercise can commence to bring a dispute to rest.

Courts of co-ordinate status with the High Court include the Federal High Court, High Court of the Federal Capital Territory, Abuja, Sharia Court of Appeal, Customary Court of Appeal and Industrial Court.⁷ Each court has its jurisdiction streamlined by the provisions of the constitution to prevent interference in adjudication and promote quick dispensation of justice. For example, the Federal High Court has the sole jurisdiction to hear and determine certain category of cases which include admiralty matters while the Sharia Court of Appeal of a State has the exclusive jurisdiction to adjudicate on matters which includes questions of Islamic personal law regarding a marriage concluded in accordance with that law, validity or dissolution of such marriage, family relationship under Islam and the guardianship of an infant whose parents are Muslims.⁸ However, an appeal against the decision of any of the courts listed above lies first at the Court of Appeal and thereafter at the Supreme Court.

The State High Court appears to be the most patronized Court amongst the aforementioned courts which litigants seek for judicial services in the resolution of agitating legal issues. The above may be due to the fact that the trial of both common disputes and heinous crimes fall within the purview of the State High Court. Thus, whether the dispute between parties emanates from a simple contractual agreement of a liquidate sum which is above the limit of the Magistrate Court or the case is one of murder, the State High Court is empowered to conduct the adjudication process.⁹

The constitution provides for the existence of one High Court for each State of the federation.¹⁰ The various judicial divisions of a State High Court exist for the purposes of administrative convenience.¹¹ Perhaps, it is the constitutional backing which the State High Court enjoys that qualifies all matters brought before it to be termed matters before a court of competent jurisdiction.¹² The Court will be duly constituted where one judge sits to hear and determine a case be it civil or criminal and whether

⁷ Section 6 subsections (3) and (5) of the Constitution; Section 1 subsection (3) paragraph (a) of the National Industrial Court Act, 2006

⁸ E Malemi *Outline of Nigerian Legal System* (Lagos; Grace Publishers Inc., 1999) p 118

⁹ Ibid

¹⁰ Section 270 (1) of the Constitution

¹¹ The Nigerian Law School (n. 3)

¹² ibid

at its original or appellate stage. The constitution appears to have saddled the Court with enormous and intricate responsibilities in dispute resolution which performance demands great caution, in-depth legal knowledge and mastery of multidisciplinary skills. All of the above may not be found in one judge and where they are found, it may not all be articulated or well utilized while deciding cases on appeal due to pressure of work. The present practice has left less to be desired in the judgments delivered on appeal matters pending before High Courts. Yet, the Court has the prerequisite mechanisms to sieve and balance the legal issues that may have missed the attention of the first instance adjudicator or validate what transpired at that level. This paper explores the inhibitions to justice over appellate cases determined by State High Courts with the view of bringing to the fore the need for a change in the status quo ante to forestall enviable justice at that level. The paper captures its theme under five parts. Part 1 is the introduction. Part II presents background literature to appellate adjudication with emphasis on appellate jurisdiction of State High Courts assumed concurrently with its original and supervisory jurisdictions. Part III highlights the dangers in appellate adjudication done by one adjudicator at the High Court level. In Part IV, the paper makes a comparative analysis of appellate practices of intermediate courts in selected jurisdictions. Part V contains the conclusion to the paper.

1.1 Research Method

The analysis of legal texts, statutes and case law used in this work is based on doctrinal research method. The doctrinal research method is chosen because of its orderly and planned procedures which align with legal research method of identifying legal issues, interpreting them applying known legal principles in resolving what may have given rise to the identified issues.

The primary materials for this study include legal texts and statute namely; the constitution,¹³ case laws that interpret and apply constitutional provisions on appellate jurisdictions of High Courts and scholarly articles on the basis and importance of appellate adjudication of intermediate courts.

The discussion of the paper begins with background literature on the nature of appellate jurisdiction and the courts constitutionally empowered to hear appeal cases. This is followed by the analysis of the legal implications of limiting appellate adjudication conducted by an intermediate court to a lone adjudicator's evaluation of

¹³ The Constitution (n. 1)

the issues raised in a case submitted for re-examination. The paper discusses further the mechanisms employed in other jurisdictions for the consideration of cases on appeal brought before intermediate courts and the effectiveness of such practices when compared to the one involving a lone adjudicator.

Data analysis methods include qualitative analysis which involves interpreting legal texts, statutes and case law were employed to identity the theme and issues in appellate adjudication in High Courts. Comparative analysis evaluates the differences in appellate practices of intermediate courts in selected jurisdictions – comparing the procedural requirements such as the composition of adjudicators, their qualification and experience and the nature of reception given to the outcome of the adjudication process.

In addition to the above, the paper was thorough in all its analysis and in the procedural steps employed in gathering all relevant legal texts, statutes and case law on appellate jurisdiction as well as in the review of literature on appellate jurisdiction to ensure that the research can be replicated.

2. BACKGROUND LITERATURE TO APPELLATE ADJUDICATION AND THE EXERCISE OF THE SAME BY STATE HIGH COURTS

Justice appears to be the much sought after outcome of any adjudication process.¹⁴ In a formal court setting, justice is sought through the application of the provisions of the law to cases brought before the Court after due interpretation of the same.¹⁵ It is the Court which gives the real meaning of the law through the judgment it passes in various cases.¹⁶ The meaning of the law given by the Court is relied upon in the determination of disputes in which the judicial system is invoked.

The judgment delivered by various courts play a number of roles namely; it provides the means through which adjudication is brought to an end and/or becomes binding upon lower courts. For example, judgment brings litigation between disputing parties to an end and can also be the basis for further litigation that will also be determined by the judgment of another higher court. The process may continue until it gets to the apex court where the last final decision is given in a matter and that decision is final forever except there is a legislature on the contrary.¹⁷

¹⁴ Noida Int. Uni <<https://niu.edu.in>> accessed 28 August 2024

¹⁵ *ibid*

¹⁶ *ibid*

¹⁷ *Adigun v. A. G. Oyo State* (1987) 2NWLR (Pt. 197 @ 214

Matters deserving appellate adjudication are different from those heard at first instance where an adjudicator assumes original jurisdiction.¹⁸ An appeal may be seen as the process of removing a case to a higher tribunal.¹⁹ An appeal does not just move to a higher tribunal but has to originate from an inferior tribunal which adjudication process and result have shown that there is the need for a re-examination or review or reversal or retrial or modification to be carried out at a higher level of adjudication.²⁰ Thus, the main purpose of an appeal is to put right any mistake made inadvertently or otherwise in the adjudication process conducted by an inferior or higher court whether in its adjudication process, judgment or in its sentence order.²¹

The Court approached for the review of the decisions of the court of first instance or the decisions of an administrative agency is a court empowered with appellate jurisdiction.²² Appellate adjudication is conducted by superior courts which in some jurisdiction are styled as Supreme Court, Court of Appeal and other intermediate courts.²³ The decision reached by the court under its appellate jurisdiction form the basis of the decision made by higher courts and the decisions of the latter courts while conducting appellate adjudication becomes a point of reference to the inferior courts.²⁴ Those judicial decisions account for one source of law.²⁵

Appellate adjudication may be invoked for a number of reasons one of which is to review discretionary powers or ruling of the first instance adjudicator in a case.²⁶ The trial Court may have exercised its discretionary to allow a request from a party to continue or to amend their pleadings or to file documents late.²⁷ The discretion may be queried, thus, requiring the appellate Court's decision. A court's exercise of discretion may be overturned on grounds of abuse if the trial adjudicator did not exercise sound, reasonable and legal decision-making skills.²⁸ It could be that the correct law was not applied or that the correct law which was applied was given a

¹⁸ A. O. Oyebiyi 'Preparation of Records of Appeal: Role of Registrars and Court Clerks' (2014) Vol. 10 *NJI*

¹⁹ The Chambers 20th Century Dictionary (AM McDonald edn., 1981) p. 59

²⁰ The Webster's Collegiate Dictionary (5th edn.) p. 51 (referenced in Oyebiyi (n. 18)

²¹ <<https://www.wicourts.gov>> accessed 29 August 2024

²² Black's Law Dictionary (5th edn.) p. 51 (referenced in Oyebiyi (n. 18).

²³ Sections 233, 240 and 257 of the Constitution (n. 1)

²⁴ Oyebiyi (n. 18)

²⁵ Noida Int. Uni (n.

²⁶ A Hayes 'What are Appellate Courts? How They Work and Functions' <investo.com> accessed 29 August 2024

²⁷ *ibid*

²⁸ *ibid*

wrong interpretation or that the decision reached by the Court was based on inaccurate view of law or of findings of material facts.²⁹ An abuse of discretion will be self-evident where there is no evidence on the record book to support the Court's decision.³⁰ An appellate court may review a case in which the issue presented is simply that of law or facts or a mixture of factual and legal issue.³¹ It is of law where the interpretation of a statute is involved.³² Appeal on facts would address issues on the composition of the court while a mixture of law and fact will present itself in a single appeal. Where the issue of law tends to dominate, a de novo standard of evaluation is employed.³³ With a mixed question of law and fact, the standard to adopt by the appellate court depends on which of the two either factual or legal will dominates or controls the court's decision. The trial court's decision after an appropriate examination, may be overturned or upheld. In the former case, the trial court's judgment is substituted with that of the appellate court while in the latter, the original decision is left undisturbed.

2.1 Appellate Jurisdiction of State High Courts

The original jurisdiction of State High Courts to wit: power to conduct trial in any civil matter in which a dispute arises from the legal rights and obligations of the disputing parties, power to hear from the onset and subsequently make categorical statements on the culpability of offenders in criminal proceedings and power to determine the appropriate verdict namely; damages, fine, forfeitures and punishments for wrong doers make up just one aspect of the court's constitutional obligations.³⁴ The other aspect is its duty to hear and determine both interlocutory appeals and appeals over matters which though may have been concluded by the lower court where it was first heard but has been adjudged by one of the parties in the case not to have the face of justice.³⁵

The appellate powers of the State High Court are different from those it exercises as a trial court.³⁶ In exercise of appellate jurisdiction, the court is obligated to preserve the decision of the lower/trial court that promotes justice or amend same where if left

²⁹ ibid

³⁰ Ibid

³¹ ibid

³² Oyebiyi (n. 18)

³³ ibid

³⁴ Section 272 of the Constitution; Malemi (n. 8)

³⁵ ibid

³⁶ Tom Anyafulude in P Nnaemeka-Agu (CON) *Manual of Brief Writing in the Court of Appeal and the Supreme Court of Nigeria* (Syon Prints Ventures Ltd. 2010) p. 9

unaltered would result to substantial miscarriage of justice.³⁷ In *Asolo v Asolo*,³⁸ the court held that appellate jurisdiction of a court empowers it to amend the record of the trial court so as to comply with what is proved before it and the decision given by it. The court held further that the duty to amend will arise where it is perceived that the decision of the lower court will lead to a miscarriage of justice.³⁹ However, caution must be exercised to ward off arbitrary exercise of discretion to permit amendment.⁴⁰ Explicitly, appellate powers entail inter alia:

- (i) power to make pronouncements that will help resolve disagreements;⁴¹
- (ii) power to rectify any error in the record of proceedings of the trial court;
- (iii) power to request a lower court to revisit its trial proceedings and certify the findings it might it might have made;
- (iv) power to make an interim order/injunction which the lower court is empowered to make;⁴²
- (v) power to take over the whole proceedings as if the proceedings have been instituted in the court with appellate jurisdiction;
- (vi) power to hear a case in part or whole;⁴³
- (vii) power to refer a case to the lower court which heard it for the case to be reheard and
- (viii) power to give specifications to the court below on how to deal with a case.⁴⁴

The above powers are exercised over interlocutory and substantive matters. Interlocutory applications originate from the Court where the substantive case is pending.⁴⁵ They are applications which require the Court to make interim orders which shall sub-exist for the time being upon the application of any of the parties in the case pending before it until the substantive matter is determined.⁴⁶ They are essentially discretionary orders of Court made judicially and judiciously with regard to facts and

³⁷ ibid

³⁸ (1996) 2 NWLR (Pt. 431) 480 @ 481-482

³⁹ ibid

⁴⁰ ibid

⁴¹ Anyafulude (n. 15)

⁴² ibid

⁴³ ibid

⁴⁴ ibid

⁴⁵ S Nwannekanma 'Interlocutory Applications' (The Guardian Newspaper; Tuesday June 15, 2010)

⁴⁶ Hon Justice F O Ibiam 'Interlocutory Proceedings in the Magistrates' Courts: Guiding Principles' (2016) *NJI* (Being paper delivered at the Orientation Course for Newly Appointed Magistrates)

circumstances that are connected to the substantive case yet to be finalized so as to ensure that justice in the case is not marred.⁴⁷ In *Solanko v Ajibola*,⁴⁸ the Court reiterated the above objective of interlocutory applications when it held thus: “interlocutory pleadings are vital and essential in proceedings and in the general administration of justice.”⁴⁹

Interlocutory applications include application for injunctions (both ex-parte and on notice), stay of proceedings, stay of execution, enforcement of judgments, instalmental payment, contempt of Court, bail pending appeal and preliminary objections.⁵⁰ An interlocutory application is made an object of appeal where either of the parties in a case appears dissatisfied with the ruling given by the lower Court. Thus, the Court which assumes appellate jurisdiction is required to review the ruling of the first Court and either exercise its discretion differently where it feels there is a wrongful exercise of discretion by that Court or leave the ruling untouched because it finds no cogent reason to substitute its own discretion with that of the lower Court.⁵¹

Interlocutory applications over the ruling of the Court below it. The intermediate Court while exercising its powers derived from Constitutional provisions, statutory provisions of the court, the rules of the court or the court’s inherent powers; may inter alia order an interlocutory injunction (whether ex-parte or on notice with the sole purpose of protecting the rights of the applicants and preserving the object of litigation); sit over an application for bail pending an appeal (to grant conditional freedom to a convict who desires to exercise his right of appeal); or determine an application for preliminary objection (consider whether on the basis of what has occurred or about to occur in a case, an intermediate decision would be needed to prevent the Court from embarking on a futile legal process.⁵² The above got judicial backing in *Obioha v Military Administrator Imo State*,⁵³ *Effiong v COP*⁵⁴ and *Rabiu v Adebayo*⁵⁵ respectively.

47 Nwannekanma (n. 24)

48 (1968) 1 ALL NLR 46, 51

49 ibid

50 Ibiam (n. 25)

51 *Kasuma v Shitta Bey & Ors* (2007) ALL FWLR (Pt. 356) 741, 768, 578 Cited in Ibiam.

52 Ibiam (n. 25)

53 (1998) 10 NWLR (Pt. 569) p. 205

54 (1967) NMLR 341

55 (2012) 15 NWLR (Pt. 1322) p. 125

The specification of the law on rulings over interlocutory appeals seems tasking because of the twin elements which must co-exist in the decision reached. The first of the element is that the guidelines laid down in well-established judicial authorities must be followed and the second is that the Court is enjoined to be cautious while exercising its discretion which it is allowed to do.⁵⁶ The guidelines which are concrete and objective may not be easily interpreted as required by law just as discretion which is mainly subjective may be tinted with purposes other than good faith particularly with reference to ex-parte applications.⁵⁷

The inconsistency in rulings of such nature may be attributed to the fact that a Court that is solely constituted may find it difficult to give a holistic appreciation of all the issues raised in an application and thus, distinguish frivolous matters in which legal process is sought to perfect ill intentions from matters that are laced with serious issues to be determined. Yet, the relief for interlocutory applications is consistent and may appear punitive so, deserve to be treated with caution after due process of the law has been followed.⁵⁸ Therefore, interlocutory applications considered at appeal level by some State High Courts need proper evaluation of issues and that may not be found in a One Man Court.

Appeals on substantive matters require a thorough and in-depth analysis of law in offences which lower courts have jurisdiction to try. The offences include conspiracy, threatening violence, stealing, receiving stolen goods, breaking and entry, assault, assault occasioning grievous harm and malicious damage.⁵⁹ The adjudication process followed by the lower Court in cases for which any of the above offences are alleged could be the subject of appeal at the State High Court if any of the parties in each case showed dissatisfaction with the procedure, judgment or even the sentence passed by that Court. The Court assuming appellate jurisdiction can only do justice as required by law where all faculties including experience and patience are brought to book and same may be found in a court that is composed of more than one judicial officer.

Appeals on interlocutory and substantive matters at the intermediate court level are germane legal issues which if undermined could lead to a miscarriage of justice that

⁵⁶ *Kotoye v CBN* (1989) 1 NWLR (Pt. 98) p. 49

⁵⁷ *Ibiam* (n. 25)

⁵⁸ *ibid*

⁵⁹ Sections 516; 86; 383; 427; 412; 253; 355; 451 of Criminal Law Cap C21, Laws of Delta State 2006 (hereinafter referred to as Criminal Law)

may not be corrected where the zeal to continue with litigation and the financial capacity to do same is lacking. It becomes imperative to review the appellate composition of some State High Courts considering the fact that the Court is also saddled with other matters in which it has original jurisdiction and must do justice at all instances.

3. THE PERILS OF SOLITARY APPELLATE DECISIONS OF STATE HIGH COURTS

The constitution provides that for a State High Court to be duly composed by at least one judge in its original, appellate or supervisory jurisdiction.⁶⁰ The phrase used in the constitution for the composition of judges who sit and determine cases at State High Courts is ‘at least’ and by the canons of interpretation, words used in the statute which are direct, straight forward and unambiguous should attract the ordinary meanings given to them.⁶¹ The word ‘least’ ordinarily depicts something smallest in size and degree.⁶² Where it is used with the preposition ‘at’ to give ‘at least’, the meaning becomes not less than that smallest number or degree that is intended.⁶³ It follows that from plain rule of literal interpretation, ‘at least’ implies not less than the smallest number which is one but could also be more than that smallest number, thus; two or more judges sitting over a particular matter at the High Court will not be unconstitutional.

The above position seems strengthened by rules of court in some parts of Nigeria.⁶⁴ The Supreme Court decision in *Ishola v Abioye*⁶⁵ which overruled its earlier position in *Oloriegbe v Omotosho*⁶⁶ shows that State High Courts can be composed of more than one judge particularly when determining appellate cases. The Court in the former case noted that the use of the phrase ‘at least one judge’ implies that the constitution envisages a situation where more than one High Court judge will sit over a matter.⁶⁷ Yet, the practice in some parts of Nigeria is that one judge sits to determine

⁶⁰ Section 279 of the Constitution.

⁶¹ A D Badaiki *Interpretation of Statutes* (1st edn; Tiken Publishers, 1996) p. 20

⁶² A S Hornby Oxford Advanced Learner’s Dictionary (8th edn; Oxford University Press, 2010).

⁶³ *ibid*

⁶⁴ Section 63 of the High Court Laws of Northern Nigeria.1963

⁶⁵ (1994) 7-8 SCNJ p. 1@ 36

⁶⁶ (1993) 1 SCNJ p. 30

⁶⁷ *Ibid*

all cases brought before the High Court be it cases at the original or appellate stage or even cases requiring the Court's supervisory role.

The consequences of such practice are enormous even though it may be whittled down to discourage wide spread public outcry and a total write-off of the judiciary as well as what it portends. The unguided exercise of discretionary powers in the grant of ex-parte injunctions by State High Courts in Southern Nigeria seems to be top in the list of dangers which follow the practice of constituting only one judge to hear certain matters.⁶⁸ In *Echaka Cattle Ranch Ltd v NACB Ltd*,⁶⁹ the Supreme Court lamented over the incessant abuse of ex-parte injunctions by courts despite the repeated warnings against same.⁷⁰ The Court held thus;

"...it is observed that the order of interlocutory injunction was made ... without hearing the defendant. It is strange after all that has been said and written on the grant of injunction pending the determination of an action. This is to say the least, is very unfortunate.⁷¹ The interlocutory injunction which was not made an issue for determination at the Supreme Court was granted by the State High Court. The apex court again enunciated the justification for the grant of ex-parte injunctions which must be done sparingly. The reasons are equally contained in the decision reached in *Sabru Nigeria Ltd v Jezco Nigeria Ltd*⁷² where it was held that the principle governing the administration of justice frowns at the condemnation of a man who has not been heard so his side of the story and probable defence can only be imagined which is not proper.⁷³ However, the Court added that in extreme situations where the preservation of the subject of the suit is needed for justice to be done, and same is in danger of being destroyed by one party... then one of the parties can come to Court in the absence of the other for an application to preserve that subject and the grant of the application would be based on the fact that delay would involve greater injustice than the instant action.⁷⁴

Although, the abuse stated in the last but one case, has been addressed through sanctions given by the National Judicial Council, the last of the problem may not have

⁶⁸ Ibiam (n. 25)

⁶⁹ (1998) 56/57 LCRN 3333 per Ogundare JSC.

⁷⁰ *ibid*

⁷¹ *Ibid* p. 14

⁷² (2001) 2 NWLR (Pt. 697) 364 @ 380

⁷³ *ibid*

⁷⁴ *ibid*

been heard. Interlocutory appeals need to be properly handled by State High Courts because most litigants end their adjudication career at that level. The present situation where matters on appeal which could have been successfully concluded at the intermediate court level proceed to Court of Appeal and decisions made at the former courts are either set aside or sent back to be reviewed is uncalled for and a mere judicial waste of time and resources. Cases will definitely go on appeal but where rulings or decisions on substantive matters which began at the lower courts are frequently overruled after they have been reviewed by State High Courts, leaves nothing to be desired by the justice delivery system. The judicial process may need an overhaul in the composition of intermediate courts for adjudication process to be enhanced.

Again, with an increased number of judicial officers who hear appeals from lower courts, a more robust judicial system may be installed at the State High Court level. The system will give room for a healthy application of the law and true evaluation of evidence given in court particularly when same is matched with witness's demeanour while giving or listening to evidence given about them. The evaluation of the entire adjudication process by two or more judges will be better than that observed by one judge. The former may limit the law to the narrow perception of the court while the latter will produce extended objective views which when put together will project the judiciary in a better light. The latter when vigorously pursued may produce minority decisions which may turn out to be the engine of reforms in our laws. So, insisting on solitary composition of State High Courts appears to undermine advancement in law and the growth of its personnel.

A practice that allows more than one adjudicator to review a case at the High Court will help restore the confidence of dissatisfied parties and other on-lookers of the judicial process in the adjudicatory system.⁷⁵ The practice will eliminate the suspicion that all the component parts of justice may not have been evaluated by a one-man court because alternative forum of resolution of both legal and factual issues in a case would be easily seen and appreciated. Again, such practice will promote the systematic development of law because appellate adjudication encourages a more detailed appraisal of the issues sieved from a dispute which analysis by more than one

⁷⁵ Oyebiyi (n.18)

adjudicator will make the law more certain for ease of comprehension by the citizenry.⁷⁶

Perhaps, the nexus between increased composition of judges of State High Courts and job creation has not been properly understood by persons in authority. What may appear hidden is that a change in policy which will further the intendment of the objective of the constitution as per composition of State High Courts will also create job opportunities for the number of legal professionals who have attained the mandatory number of years to be appointed judges. Thus, with improved administration of justice and increased job chances for lawyers, the judiciary will regain some of its lost glory, one of which is excluding the Almighty, it is the last hope of the common man.

4. **COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF COMPOSITION OF COURTS WHILE ASSUMING APPELLATE JURISDICTION IN SELECTED JURISDICTION**

Courts in other jurisdictions which seem to occupy similar position as well as perform duties in their original and appellate capacity as State High Courts do appear to be differently composed while carrying out the latter task. In some jurisdictions, the presiding judicial officers may be two or more and in others, a judge is assisted by lay persons to arrive at a conclusive decision over an appeal matter pending before him for determination. What seems to be of notorious practice in developed countries appears to discourage solitary appellate adjudication.

The United States of America appears to operate both a National Court Structure and a State Court System.⁷⁷ In the former, appeal lies to the United States Court of Appeal as next in hierarchy to the lower court being the court of first instance.⁷⁸ The Court of first instance is also empowered to determine rulings of administrative tribunals and the food and drug administration. Thus, like Federal High Courts in Nigeria, they have specialized jurisdiction but unlike their Nigerian counterparts, they are composed of three or more judges where they have to determine whether the law has been properly

⁷⁶ ibid

⁷⁷ M G Reskin el ta Political Science: An Introduction (11th edn; Longman, 2010)

⁷⁸ ibid

interpreted or rightly applied in the appeal brought before it and draws conclusion on the case based on majority vote.⁷⁹

At the State Court System, original jurisdiction is exercised in both civil and criminal cases. The above appear to be in line with the jurisdiction of State High Courts in Nigeria. The Magistrate Courts at the urban areas have jurisdiction to hear and determine minor matters and pass judgments such as fines and short jail terms like their Nigerian counterparts.⁸⁰ Appeal over the decisions of both lower courts go to the State Courts. However, the State Courts in the United States operate a jury system. The jury may hear the case but a judge enlightens its members on the probative value of the evidence given and the weight to be attached to same. The applicable laws to be relied upon is laid down by the judge in both civil and criminal cases.⁸¹ So, the jury may determine the guilt of a person charged with a criminal offence but it does that under the instruction of a judge.⁸² The adjudication process highlighted above gives room for alternative decisions which when harnessed would have addressed the law properly such that litigants will also appreciate the evaluation process. Nigeria appears to lack such alternative appraisal mechanism in its appellate adjudication at the State High Courts which may be responsible for the doubts casted on the appellate judgments emanating from the Court.

The French Courts seem to represent what operates in most European Courts. A judge may sit alone while considering a case on appeal to determine whether legal procedures and law were followed by the lower Court but at the end, a jury sits to consider the judgment to be given and the sentence that will be passed thereafter.⁸³ The practice adopted under the system allows for a wide difference in the judgment and sentencing pattern of the lower/inferior court and that employed for the appellate review. Where only a sole adjudicator is responsible for the adjudication processes in both the original and appellate judicial system, not much confidence will exist in the minds of persons who have moved from the lower court to the higher court with the hope of getting an enhanced justice system. A change in the present system to reflect what obtains in some other jurisdictions as far as appellate adjudication is concerned

⁷⁹ *ibid*

⁸⁰ Magistrates' Courts Laws cap M1, Laws of Delta State, 2006

⁸¹ Reskin (n. 54)

⁸² *ibid*

⁸³ *ibid*

at the High Court level will promote stability in the law as well as forestall remarkable differences in the adjudication processes at the lower and higher court systems. The result of which may bring to an end the era of arbitrary pronouncements from the High Courts over same or similar issues presented at that level for a re-examination.

In Nigeria, courts of co-ordinate jurisdiction as State High Courts are properly constituted to hear appeal cases where more than one judge is adjudicator. Customary Court of Appeal is one of such courts just as it is the case at Sharia Court of Appeal. In each case, three judges/three kadis must sit at the same time and throughout the period of adjudication for the jurisdiction of the Court not to be queried.⁸⁴ Although, the last two courts have specialized appellate jurisdiction, the law still deems it wise to allow more than one judge to determine the appeal cases pending there. Therefore, the extension of such practice to the State High Courts when they assume appellate jurisdiction may not constitute any harm, rather, it will promote the appellate adjudication system and make it even across all intermediate courts in the country.

5. CONCLUSION

State High Courts occupy important position in the adjudication of cases. The quality of judgment given by the Court can significantly impact the administration of justice in cases particularly when further appeal on such cases may be frustrated due to finance or other personal reasons. When solitary decisions are made by the Court on the slightest opportunity to appeal and such decision is marred by inexperience, or lack of proper understanding of the law, the hope of persons getting justice in their cases may be dashed. Furthermore, such may not be the answer to advancement in law which must grow at the same speed with changes in the society.

This paper has found that limiting appellate decisions at State High Courts to lone observations and interpretations of the law may hamper positive growth in law and society. The paper recommends the adoption of proper interpretation of statutory provisions for the composition of State High Courts when deciding appeal cases. The paper has re-affirmed the need for a change in the existing composition of State High Courts while assuming appellate jurisdiction.

⁸⁴ Sections 268 and 283; 263 and 278 of the Constitution respectively.